

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: DSDD

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: KABIRU

Edit or delete text to show actual information below: UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)The author used the following software: (Office 365 on Windows10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

INSTRUCTION: Check the box of the correct answer

1. Style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent (EUCLID ACA-401D 2015, 52). Style guides are generally associated with certain types and they include:

- Scientific, technical, humanities and behavioural writings.
- Mathematical, academic, personal and philosophical writings.
- Technical, commercial/business, journalism and web copy writings.¹**
- Journalism, academic, scientific and professional writings.

¹ EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 12, 2019), 52-54.

- 2. The body of an essay consists of paragraphs. Each paragraph is a building block in the construction of arguments. The body is where you:**
- Restate your answer to the question.
 - Re-summarise the main points.
 - Answer the question with a thesis statement.
 - show your knowledge and grasp of material you have read.²**
- 3. The reasons for source citation include one of the following:**
- To show readers the research tradition that informs your work.³**
 - To restate your reasons and group evidence under them.
 - Who wrote, edited, or translated the text.
 - Record all bibliographical information before taking notes.
- 4. In recording bibliographic data, one of the options below is not required.**
- Who published the source and when?
 - Who evaluated the relevance of sources?⁴**
 - Who assembled the source?
 - What data identify the source?
- 5. Different readers expect researchers to ask and answer different kinds of questions. Which of the options below is not expected of the researcher?**
- Applied Questions.
 - Conceptual Questions.

² Ibid, 4.

³ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013, 86.

⁴ Ibid, 28-87.

- Inferred Questions.**⁵
- Practical Questions.
- 6. Generally, researchers in the humanities often quote while social and natural scientists characteristically paraphrase and summarise. What is one of the purposes for quoting?**
- The quoted words express your key concepts so intriguingly.**⁶
- The quoted word can state what a source says more concisely.
- The quoted word can weave the grammar of the quotation into the grammar of your sentence.
- The quoted word is important enough to warrant more space.
- 7. The use of multiple methods and triangulation is critical in attempting to obtain an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under study. What does the strategy not add to the study?**
- Rigour.
- Insight.**⁷
- Breadth.
- Depth.
- 8. The data generated by qualitative methods are huge, and the sheer quantity of raw data can indeed be quite daunting. If data are to be thoroughly analysed, they must be:**
- Well managed
- Well organised.**⁸
- Well understood.

⁵ Ibid, 15

⁶ Ibid, 49

⁷ Bloomberg, Linda D. & Volpe, Marie. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 82.

⁸ Ibid, 126

Well interpreted.

9. Abbreviations in the broad sense can be classed into two main categories and each in turn divided into two sub-categories. What are the two categories abbreviations can be grouped into?

Contractions and truncations.

Truncations and Acronyms.

Acronyms and Initialisms.⁹

Initialisms and Contractions.

10. What are the other financial institutions of the European Union?

European Financial Organisation and European Social Fund.

European Investment Bank and European Investment Fund.¹⁰

European Central Bank and Investment Bank of the European Union.

European Development Bank and European Investment Fund.

⁹ The European Commission. English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission, 26

¹⁰ Ibid, 67

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D. & Volpe, Marie. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008.

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed February 12, 2020).

European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. 2011. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Seventh edition. European Commission.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

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